

A GENERAL RESULT ON THE SMARANDACHE STAR FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT: In this paper ,the result (theorem-2.6) Derived in REF. [2], the paper "Generalization Of Partition Function, Introducing 'Smarandache Factor Partition' which has been observed to follow a beautiful pattern has been generalized.

DEFINITIONS In [2] we define SMARANDACHE FACTOR PARTITION FUNCTION , as follows:

Let $\alpha_1 , \alpha_2 , \alpha_3 , \dots \alpha_r$ be a set of r natural numbers and $p_1 , p_2, p_3 , \dots p_r$ be arbitrarily chosen distinct primes then $F(\alpha_1 , \alpha_2 , \alpha_3 , \dots \alpha_r)$ called the Smarandache Factor Partition of $(\alpha_1 , \alpha_2 , \alpha_3 , \dots \alpha_r)$ is defined as the number of ways in which the number

$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ could be expressed as the

product of its' divisors. For simplicity , we denote $F(\alpha_1 , \alpha_2 , \alpha_3 , \dots \alpha_r) = F' (N)$,where

$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r} \dots p_n^{\alpha_n}$

and p_r is the r^{th} prime. $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3$ etc.

Also for the case

$$\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \alpha_3 = \dots = \alpha_r = \dots = \alpha_n = 1$$

we denote

$$F(1, 1, 1, 1, 1, \dots) = F(1\#n)$$

← n - ones →

Smarandache Star Function

$$(1) \quad F^*(N) = \sum_{d|N} F'(d_r) \quad \text{where } d_r | N$$

$$(2) \quad F^{**}(N) = \sum_{d_r|N} F'^*(d_r)$$

d_r ranges over all the divisors of N .

If N is a square free number with n prime factors, let us denote

$$F^{**}(N) = F^{**}(1\#n)$$

Here we generalise the above idea by the following definition

Smarandache Generalised Star Function

$$(3) \quad F'^{n*}(N) = \sum_{d_r|N} F'^{(n-1)*}(d_r) \quad n > 1$$

and d_r ranges over all the divisors of N .

For simplicity we denote

$$F'(Np_1p_2 \dots p_n) = F'(N@1\#n), \text{ where}$$

$(N, p_i) = 1$ for $i = 1$ to n and each p_i is a prime.

$F'(N@1\#n)$ is nothing but the Smarandache factor partition of (a number N multiplied by n primes which are coprime to N).

In [3] a proof of the following result is given:

$$F'(Np_1p_2p_3) = F''(N) + 3F''^2(N) + F''^3(N)$$

The present paper aims at generalising the above result.

DISCUSSION:

THEOREM(3.1)

$$F'(N@1\#n) = F'(Np_1p_2 \dots p_n) = \sum_{m=0}^n [a_{(n,m)} F''^m(N)]$$

where

$$a_{(n,m)} = (1/m!) \sum_{k=1}^m (-1)^{m-k} \cdot {}^m C_k \cdot k^n$$

PROOF:

Let the divisors of N be

$$d_1, d_2, \dots, d_k$$

Consider the divisors of $(Np_1p_2 \dots p_n)$ arranged as follows

$$d_1, d_2, \dots, d_k \quad \text{-----say type (0)}$$

$$d_1p_i, d_2p_i, \dots, d_kp_i \quad \text{-----say type (1)}$$

$$d_1p_ip_j, d_2p_ip_j, \dots, d_kp_ip_j \quad \text{-----say type (2)}$$

$$d_1p_ip_j \dots, d_2p_ip_j \dots, \dots, d_kp_ip_j \dots \quad \text{-----say type (t)}$$

(there are t primes in the term $d_1p_ip_j \dots$ apart from d_1)

$$d_1p_1p_2 \dots p_n, d_2p_1p_2 \dots p_n, \dots, d_np_1p_2 \dots p_n, \quad \text{-----say type (n)}$$

There are ${}^n C_0$ divisors sets of the type (0)

There are ${}^n C_1$ divisors sets of the type (1)

There are ${}^n C_2$ divisors sets of the type (2) and so on

There are ${}^n C_t$ divisors sets of the type (t)

There are ${}^n C_n$ divisor sets of the type (n)

Let $Np_1p_2 \dots p_n = M$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 F^*(M) = & {}^n C_0 [\text{sum of the factor partitions of all the divisors of row (0)}] \\
 & + {}^n C_1 [\text{sum of the factor partitions of all the divisors of row (1)}] \\
 & + {}^n C_2 [\text{sum of the factor partitions of all the divisors of row (2)}] \\
 & + \dots \\
 & + {}^n C_t [\text{sum of the factor partitions of all the divisors of row (t)}] \\
 & + \dots \\
 & + {}^n C_n [\text{sum of the factor partitions of all the divisors of row (n)}]
 \end{aligned}$$

Let us consider the contributions of divisor sets one by one.

Row (0) or type (0) contributes

$$F'(d_1) + F'(d_2) + F'(d_3) + \dots + F'(d_n) = F'^*(N)$$

Row (1) or type (1) contributes

$$\begin{aligned}
 & [F'(d_1p_1) + F'(d_2p_1) + \dots + F'(d_kp_1)] \\
 = & [F'^*(d_1) + F'^*(d_2) + \dots + F'^*(d_k)] \\
 = & F'^{2*}(N)
 \end{aligned}$$

Row (2) or type (2) contributes

$$[F'(d_1p_1p_2) + F'(d_2p_1p_2) + \dots + F'(d_kp_1p_2)]$$

Applying theorem (5) on each of the terms

$$F'(d_1p_1p_2) = F'^*(d_1) + F'^{3*}(d_1) \quad \text{----(1)}$$

$$F'(d_2p_1p_2) = F'^*(d_2) + F'^{3*}(d_2) \quad \text{----(2)}$$

.

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.

$$F'(d_kp_1p_2) = F'^*(d_k) + F'^{3*}(d_k) \quad \text{----(k)}$$

on summing up (1), (2) ... upto (n) we get

$$F'^{2*}(N) + F'^{3*}(N)$$

At this stage let us denote the coefficients as $a_{(n,r)}$ etc. say

$$F'(N@1\#r) = a_{(r,1)}F'^*(N) + a_{(r,2)}F'^{2*}(N) + \dots + a_{(r,t)}F'^{t*}(N) + \dots + a_{(r,r)}F'^{r*}(N)$$

Consider row (t) , one divisor set is

$$d_1p_1p_2\dots p_t , d_2p_1p_2\dots p_t , \dots , d_kp_1p_2\dots p_t ,$$

and we have

$$F'(d_1@1\#t) = a_{(t,1)}F'^*(d_1) + a_{(t,2)}F'^{2*}(d_1) + \dots + a_{(t,t)}F'^{t*}(d_1)$$

$$F'(d_2@1\#t) = a_{(t,1)}F'^*(d_2) + a_{(t,2)}F'^{2*}(d_2) + \dots + a_{(t,t)}F'^{t*}(d_2)$$

.

.

$$F'(d_k@1\#t) = a_{(t,1)}F'^*(d_k) + a_{(t,2)}F'^{2*}(d_k) + \dots + a_{(t,t)}F'^{t*}(d_k)$$

summing up both the sides columnwise we get for row (t) or

divisors of type (t) one of the nC_t divisor sets contributes

$$a_{(t,1)}F'^{2*}(N) + a_{(t,2)}F'^{3*}(N) + \dots + a_{(t,t)}F'^{(t+1)*}(N)$$

similarly for row (n) we get

$$a_{(n,1)}F'^{2*}(N) + a_{(n,2)}F'^{3*}(N) + \dots + a_{(n,n)}F'^{(n+1)*}(N)$$

All the divisor sets of type (0) contribute

$${}^nC_0 a_{(0,0)}F'^*(N) \text{ factor partitions.}$$

All the divisor sets of type (1) contribute

$${}^nC_1 a_{(1,1)}F'^{2*}(N) \text{ factor partitions.}$$

All the divisor sets of type (2) contribute

$${}^nC_2 \{a_{(2,1)}F'^{2*}(N) + a_{(2,2)}F'^{3*}(N)\} \text{ factor partitions.}$$

All the divisor sets of type (3) contribute

$${}^nC_3 \{a_{(3,1)}F'^{2*}(N) + a_{(3,2)}F'^{3*}(N) + a_{(3,3)}F'^{4*}(N)\} \text{ factor partitions.}$$

All the divisor sets of row (t) or type (t) contribute

$${}^n C_t \{ a_{(t,1)} F'^{2*}(N) + a_{(t,2)} F'^{3*}(N) + \dots + a_{(t,t)} F'^{(t+1)*}(N) \}$$

.
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All the divisor sets of row (n) or type (n) contribute

$${}^n C_n \{ a_{(n,1)} F'^{2*}(N) + a_{(n,2)} F'^{3*}(N) + \dots + a_{(n,n)} F'^{(n+1)*}(N) \}$$

Summing up the contributions from the divisor sets of all the types

and considering the coefficient of $F'^m(N)$ for $m = 1$ to $(n+1)$ we

get, coefficient of $F'^*(N) = a_{(0,0)} = 1 = a_{(n+1,1)}$

coefficient of $F'^{2*}(N)$

$$= {}^n C_1 a_{(1,1)} + {}^n C_2 a_{(2,1)} + {}^n C_3 a_{(3,1)} + \dots + {}^n C_t a_{(t,1)} + \dots + {}^n C_n a_{(n,1)}$$

$$= a_{(n+1,2)}$$

coefficient of $F'^{3*}(N)$

$$= {}^n C_2 a_{(2,2)} + {}^n C_3 a_{(3,2)} + {}^n C_4 a_{(4,2)} + \dots + {}^n C_t a_{(t,2)} + \dots + {}^n C_n a_{(n,2)}$$

$$= a_{(n+1,3)}$$

coefficient of $F'^m(N) =$

$$a_{(n+1,m)} = {}^n C_{m-1} \cdot a_{(m-1,m-1)} + {}^n C_m \cdot a_{(m,m-1)} + \dots + {}^n C_n \cdot a_{(n,m-1)}$$

coefficient of $F'^{(n+1)*}(N) =$

$$a_{(n+1,n+1)} = {}^n C_n \cdot a_{(n,n)} = {}^n C_n \cdot {}^{n-1} C_{n-1} \cdot a_{(n-1,n-1)} = {}^n C_n \cdot {}^{n-1} C_{n-1} \cdot \dots$$

$${}^2 C_2 \cdot a_{(1,1)}$$

$$= 1$$

Consider $a_{(n+1,2)}$

$$= {}^n C_1 a_{(1,1)} + {}^n C_2 a_{(2,1)} + \dots + {}^n C_t a_{(t,1)} + \dots + {}^n C_n a_{(n,1)}$$

$$= {}^n C_1 + {}^n C_2 + \dots + {}^n C_n$$

$$= 2^n - 1$$

$$= (2^{n+1} - 2)/2$$

Consider $a_{(n+1,3)}$

$$= {}^n C_2 a_{(2,2)} + {}^n C_3 a_{(3,2)} + {}^n C_4 a_{(4,2)} + \dots + {}^n C_t a_{(t,2)} + \dots + {}^n C_n a_{(n,2)}$$

$$= {}^n C_2 (2^1 - 1) + {}^n C_3 (2^2 - 1) + {}^n C_4 (2^3 - 1) + \dots + {}^n C_n (2^{n-1} - 1)$$

$$= {}^n C_2 2^1 + {}^n C_3 2^2 + \dots + {}^n C_n 2^{n-1} - \{ {}^n C_2 + {}^n C_3 + \dots + {}^n C_n \}$$

$$= (1/2) \{ {}^n C_2 2^2 + {}^n C_3 2^3 + \dots + {}^n C_n 2^n \} - \left\{ \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r - {}^n C_1 - {}^n C_0 \right\}$$

$$= (1/2) \left\{ \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r 2^r - {}^n C_1 \cdot 2^1 - {}^n C_0 \cdot 2^0 \right\} - \{ 2^n - n - 1 \}$$

$$= (1/2) \{ 3^n - 2n - 1 \} - 2^n + n + 1$$

$$= (1/2) \{ 3^n - 2^{n+1} + 1 \} \quad \text{-----(3.1)}$$

$$= \{ 1/3! \} \{ (1) \cdot 3^{n+1} - (3) \cdot 2^{n+1} + (3) \cdot (1)^{n+1} - (1) (0)^{n+1} \}$$

Evaluating $a_{(n+1,4)}$

$$a_{(n+1,4)} = {}^n C_3 a_{(3,3)} + {}^n C_4 a_{(4,3)} + \dots + {}^n C_n a_{(n,3)}$$

$$= {}^n C_3 \{ 3^2 + 1 - 2^3 \} / 2 + {}^n C_4 \{ 3^3 + 1 - 2^4 \} / 2 + \dots + {}^n C_n \{ 3^{n-1} + 1 - 2^n \} / 2$$

$$= (1/2) \left[\{ 3^2 \cdot {}^n C_3 + 3^3 \cdot {}^n C_4 + \dots + 3^{n-1} \cdot {}^n C_n \} + \{ {}^n C_3 + {}^n C_4 + \dots + {}^n C_n \} \right. \\ \left. - \{ {}^n C_3 2^3 + {}^n C_4 2^4 + \dots + {}^n C_n 2^n \} \right]$$

$$= (1/2) \left[(1/3) \left\{ \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r 3^r - 3^2 {}^n C_2 - 3 {}^n C_1 - {}^n C_0 \right\} + \left\{ \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r - {}^n C_2 - {}^n C_1 \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - {}^n C_0 \right\} - \left\{ \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r \cdot 2^r - 2^2 {}^n C_2 - 2 {}^n C_1 - {}^n C_0 \right\} \right]$$

$$= (1/2) \left[(1/3) \{ 4^n - 9n(n-1)/2 - 3n - 1 \} + \{ 2^n - n(n-1)/2 - n - 1 \} \right]$$

$$- \{ 3^n - 4n(n-1)/2 - 2n - 1 \}$$

$$a_{(n+1,4)} = (1/4!) [(1) 4^{n+1} - (4) 3^{n+1} + (6) 2^{n+1} - (4) 1^{n+1} + 1(0)^{n+1}]$$

Observing the pattern we can explore the possibility of

$$a_{(n,r)} = (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \cdot k^n \text{ -----(3.2)}$$

which is yet to be established. Now we shall apply induction.

Let the following proposition (3.3) be true for r and all $n > r$.

$$a_{(n+1,r)} = (1/r!) \sum_{k=1}^r (-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \cdot k^{n+1} \text{ -----(3.3)}$$

Given (3.3) our aim is to prove that

$$a_{(n+1,r+1)} = (1/(r+1)!) \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} [(-1)^{(r+1)-k} \cdot {}^{r+1} C_k (k)^{n+1}]$$

we have

$$a_{(n+1,r+1)} = {}^n C_r a_{(r,r)} + {}^n C_{r+1} a_{(r+1,r)} + {}^n C_{r+2} a_{(r+2,r)} + \dots + {}^n C_n a_{(n,r)}$$

$$a_{(n+1,r+1)} = {}^n C_r \left\{ (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \cdot k^r \right\} + {}^n C_{r+1} \left\{ (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \cdot k^{r+1} \right\}$$

$$+ \dots + {}^n C_n \left\{ (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \cdot k^n \right\}$$

$$= (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \{ {}^n C_r k^r + {}^n C_{r+1} k^{r+1} + \dots + {}^n C_n k^n \}]$$

$$= (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \left\{ \sum_{q=0}^n {}^n C_q k^q - \sum_{q=0}^{r-1} {}^n C_q k^q \right\}]$$

$$= (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k (1+k)^n] - (1/r!) \sum_{q=0}^{r-1} [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \{ \sum {}^n C_q k^q \}]$$

If we denote the 1st and the second term as T_1 and T_2 , we have

$$a_{(n+1,r+1)} = T_1 - T_2 \quad \text{-----}(3.4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{consider } T_1 &= (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k (1+k)^n] \\ &= (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \{ r!/((k!)(r-k)!) \} (1+k)^n] \\ &= (1/(r+1)!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \{ (r+1)!/((k+1)!(r-k)!) \} (1+k)^{n+1}] \\ &= (1/(r+1)!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^{r+1} C_{k+1} (1+k)^{n+1}] \\ &= (1/(r+1)!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{(r+1)-(k+1)} \cdot {}^{r+1} C_{k+1} (1+k)^{n+1}] \end{aligned}$$

Let $k + 1 = s$, we get, $s = 1$ at $k = 0$ and $s = r + 1$ at $k = r$

$$= (1/(r+1)!) \sum_{s=1}^{r+1} [(-1)^{(r+1)-s} \cdot {}^{r+1} C_s (s)^{n+1}]$$

replacing s by k we get

$$= (1/(r+1)!) \sum_{k=1}^{r+1} [(-1)^{(r+1)-k} \cdot {}^{r+1} C_k (k)^{n+1}]$$

in this if we include $k = 0$ case we get

$$T_1 = (1/(r+1)!) \sum_{k=0}^{r+1} [(-1)^{(r+1)-k} \cdot {}^{r+1} C_k (k)^{n+1}] \quad \text{-----(3.5)}$$

T_1 is nothing but the right hand side member of (3.3).

To prove (3.3) we have to prove $a_{(n+1,r+1)} = T_1$

In view of (3.4) our next step is to prove that $T_2 = 0$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_2 &= (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \{ \sum_{q=0}^{r-1} {}^n C_q k^q \}] \\
&= (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \{ {}^n C_0 k^0 + {}^n C_1 k^1 + {}^n C_2 k^2 + \dots + {}^n C_{r-1} k^{r-1} \}] \\
&= (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k] + {}^n C_1 [(1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r \{(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k k\}] + \\
&{}^n C_2 [(1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r \{(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k k^2\}] + \dots + {}^n C_{r-1} [(1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r \{(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k k^{r-1}\}] \\
&= (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k] + {}^n C_1 [(1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r \{(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k k\}] + \\
&\quad [{}^n C_2 \cdot a_{(2,r)} + {}^n C_3 \cdot a_{(3,r)} + \dots + {}^n C_{r-1} \cdot a_{(r-1,r)}]
\end{aligned}$$

= X + Y + Z say where

$$X = (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k] , \quad Y = {}^n C_1 [(1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r \{(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k k\}]$$

$$Z = [{}^n C_2 \cdot a_{(2,r)} + {}^n C_3 \cdot a_{(3,r)} + \dots + {}^n C_{r-1} \cdot a_{(r-1,r)}]$$

We shall prove that $X = 0$, $Y = 0$, $Z = 0$ seperately.

$$(1) \quad X = (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k]$$

$$= (1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r [(-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_{r-k}]$$

let $r - k = w$ then we get at $k = 0$ $w = r$ and at $k = r$ $w = 0$.

$$= (1/r!) \sum_{w=r}^0 [(-1)^w \cdot {}^r C_w]$$

$$= (1/r!) \sum_{w=0}^r [(-1)^w \cdot {}^r C_w]$$

$$= (1 - 1)^r / r!$$

$$= 0$$

We have proved that $X = 0$

$$(2) \quad Y = {}^n C_1 [(1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r \{ (-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \cdot k \}]$$

$$= {}^n C_1 [(1/(r-1)!) \sum_{k=1}^r \{ (-1)^{r-1-(k-1)} \cdot {}^{r-1} C_{k-1} \}]$$

$$= {}^n C_1 [(1/(r-1)!) \sum_{k-1=0}^{r-1} \{ (-1)^{r-1-(k-1)} \cdot {}^{r-1} C_{k-1} \}]$$

$$= {}^n C_1 [(1/(r-1)!) (1 - 1)^{r-1}$$

$$= 0$$

We have proved that $Y = 0$

(3) To prove

$$Z = [{}^n C_2 \cdot a_{(2,r)} + {}^n C_3 \cdot a_{(3,r)} + \dots + {}^n C_{r-1} \cdot a_{(r-1,r)}] = 0 \quad \text{----(3.6)}$$

Proof:

Refer the matrix

<u>a_(1,1)</u>	<u>a_(1,2)</u>	<u>a_(1,3)</u>	<u>a_(1,4)</u>	...	<u>a_(1,r)</u>
a _(2,1)	<u>a_(2,2)</u>	<u>a_(2,3)</u>	<u>a_(2,4)</u>	...	<u>a_(2,r)</u>
a _(3,1)	a _(3,2)	<u>a_(3,3)</u>	<u>a_(3,4)</u>	...	<u>a_(3,r)</u>
a _(4,1)	a _(4,2)	a _(4,3)	<u>a_(4,4)</u>	a _(4,5) ...	<u>a_(4,r)</u>
				

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc}
 \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \underline{a_{(r-1,r-1)}} & \mathbf{a_{(r-1,r)}} & \dots & \dots \\
 \mathbf{a_{(r,1)}} & \mathbf{a_{(r,2)}} & \mathbf{a_{(r,3)}} & \dots & \mathbf{a_{(r,r-1)}} & \underline{\mathbf{a_{(r,r)}}} & &
 \end{array}$$

The Diagonal elements are underlined . And the the elements above the leading diagonal are shown with bold face.

We have

$$a_{(1,r)} = [(1/r!) \sum_{k=0}^r \{ (-1)^{r-k} \cdot {}^r C_k \}] = Y/{}^n C_1 = 0 \text{ for } r > 1$$

All the elements of the first row except $a_{(1,1)}$ (the one on the leading diagonal) are zero.

Also

$$a_{(n+1,r)} = a_{(n,r-1)} + r \cdot a_{(n,r)} \quad \text{-----(3.7)}$$

(This can be easily established by simplifying the right hand side.)

(7) gives us

$$a_{(2,r)} = a_{(1,r-1)} + r \cdot a_{(1,r)} = 0 \text{ for } r > 2$$

i.e. $a_{(2,r)}$ can be expressed as a linear combination of two elements of the first row (except the one on the leading diagonal)

$$\Rightarrow a_{(2,r)} = 0 \quad r > 2$$

Similarly $a_{(3,r)}$ can be expressed as a linear combination of two elements of the second row of the type $a_{(2,r)}$ with $r > 3$

$$\Rightarrow a_{(2,r)} = 0 \quad r > 3$$

and so on $a_{(r-1,r)} = 0$

substituting

$$a_{(2,r)} = a_{(3,r)} = \dots = a_{(r-1,r)} = 0 \text{ in (6)}$$

we get $Z = 0$

With $X = Y = Z = 0$ we get $T_2 = 0$
 or $a_{(n+1,r+1)} = T_1 - T_2 = T_1$

from (5) we have

$$T_1 = (1/(r+1)!) \sum_{k=0}^{r+1} [(-1)^{(r+1)-k} {}^{r+1}C_k (k)^{n+1}]$$

which gives

$$a_{(n+1,r+1)} = (1/(r+1)!) \sum_{k=0}^{r+1} [(-1)^{(r+1)-k} {}^{r+1}C_k (k)^{n+1}]$$

We have proved ,if the proposition (3.3) is true for r it is true for $(r+1)$ as well .We have already verified it for $1, 2, 3$ etc. Hence by induction (3.3) is true for all n .

This completes the proof of theorem (3.1) .

Remarks: This proof is quite lengthy , clumsy and heavy in algebra. The readers can try some analytic , combinatorial approach.

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